

Name of archive: OurStory Scotland Collection

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1. Organisational background and approach

OurStory Scotland's main activities include the collection, archiving and presentation of stories of the lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender (LGBT) community in Scotland. Through written, oral, and visual storytelling, the charity contributes to historical archives, education and research, exhibitions, publication, public presentation, and theatrical performance.

The organisation was founded in 2002 by a group of members of the Diverse Artists collective based at Glasgow LGBT Centre. The absence of a national LGBT+ archive for Scotland was first raised by Jaime Valentine at a Diverse Artists meeting in late 2001. The idea for a dedicated LGBT+ archive took shape through meetings with curators including those of the Glasgow Women's Library and Brighton Ourstory Project during 2002 (OurStory Scotland, n.d.). OurStory Scotland was formally constituted as an unincorporated association with Valentine as Chair in December 2002. Dom Miller-Graham replaced Jaime Valentine, who is still closely involved with the organisation, as Chair in May 2021. The organisation was recognised as a Scottish Charity (SC 035729) in July 2004 and a Scottish Charitable Incorporated Organisation in March 2015.

The project is overseen by a Board of Trustees, comprising the Chair, Secretary, and Treasurer. OurStory Scotland has been peer-led and staffed wholly by volunteers since its inception. It has received major grant funding from the Scottish Communities Action Research Fund (administered by Communities Scotland) and the Scottish Arts Council's Lottery Fund, as well as project grant funding from Creative Scotland and the Equality Network.

The purposes of OurStory Scotland as set out in its constitution are:

- i. To promote the welfare and relieve the needs of the LGBT community, which is recognised as a community subject to social exclusion, marginalisation and disadvantage.
- ii. To develop the capacity and skills of the members of the LGBT community in such a way that they are better able to identify, and help meet, their needs and to participate more fully in society.
- iii. To advance the education of the public in understanding the history, social conditions and needs of the LGBT community through research, archiving, publication and the arts.

Valentine has described OurStory Scotland as 'the world's first project to focus on multi-media storytelling with a nationwide lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender community for public representation and national museum archiving' (2016, p.1). The main aim of the project has been:

to collect, archive and present the life stories and experiences of the LGBT community in Scotland in their own words and images, since representations of our community have tended to be stereotyped and discriminatory, constructed about us rather than by and for ourselves. Our lives have often been hidden, maligned or silenced, our stories neglected, distorted or suppressed. To tell OurStory rather than a traduced version, we aimed to establish a history from within our community (Valentine, 2012a, p.31).

Figure 1 – Madame Hystoria, inviting people into the OurStory Scotland tent at Pride Aberdeen (c.2006), where more than 60 written episodes were collected in one afternoon.

From the outset, public performance, online communication, and outreach with diverse (including non-LGBT) audiences have been built into the work of creating the archive, as opposed to a traditional curation project which might treat the work of community engagement as secondary to developing and preserving a collection.¹ **[Figure 1]** The project's early oral histories were used as the basis for interactive workshops incorporating music, poetry, and the live retelling of stories, including by people other than their original creators. This reflects OurStory Scotland's insistence that:

[t]he heritage does not solely reside in the content of the stories, but in innovative methods of collecting, presenting, and re-presenting stories – the variety of narrative acts developed by and for people marginalised by sexuality and gender. These methods were devised to be appropriate to the contingency of identity, catching and rendering our fluid and variously bounded selves that are dependent on context, performance and narrative, rather than forcing or reinforcing restrictive identifications. Alternative forms of storytelling enable multiple representations of identity and, as this is a long-term open-ended project, the development of narratives over time, relating our selves again.' (Valentine, 2016, p. 2).

The project has never been driven by the priorities of experts or academics, but its community-driven approach has been enlivened by research as well as 'participatory art and narrative methods' (Valentine, 2008, no. 2 and 2016, p. 2) and is strongly rooted in queer theory.² Valentine stresses the importance of developing new methods for capturing specifically intersectional identities and contingent and open-ended life stories, in contrast to the neater, teleological narratives which have typically surrounded diversity initiatives within more traditional archives or arts projects led by non-LGBT professionals (Valentine, 2016, p. 5; see also Arondekar et al, 2015, p. 222; Butler, 2020). For example, one of the first life stories recorded as part of the project was with Nick Laird, who as a trans man came to the project with lived experience of lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender identities; in his words: "[m]y journey has been a fluid discovery of myself, claiming and rejecting identities, trying to find the one that fits best." (quoted in Valentine, 2008, no. 12). **[Figure 2]**

¹ For instance, an early public event for the project involved securing a space for an exhibition, and then inviting participants to contribute exhibits (Valentine, 2016, p. 1).

² Valentine came to the project from an academic background as Lecturer in Sociology at the University of Stirling, with a specialism in marginality and identity formation in UK and Japan.

Figure 2 – Nick Laird (donor of OurStory Scotland interview AA015), holding up his female and male birth certificates.

While adapting oral history and archiving techniques for new forms of individual storytelling, OurStory Scotland also takes a distinctive approach to community ownership over the archive. Donors are encouraged to assign their copyrights in their stories to OurStory Scotland at the point of creation but control how their words will be attributed in the future, choosing their own level of anonymity at the point of donation (full name, first name or pseudonym). Valentine describes the organisation's activities as:

collective ventures, whose products would belong to the collectivity (for public representation and archiving) rather than to separate individuals. Individual attribution may be desired or shunned, appropriate or irrelevant, but whoever the nominal creator, the work belongs to all and is donated to help form OurStory (Valentine, 2016, p. 11).

This approach to collaboration complicates traditional archival understandings of provenance as well as categorisation within cultural heritage, reflecting queer understandings of the social and discursive nature of creative production (Drabinski, 2013; Murphy et al, 2016). The collective work of storytelling, in Valentine's words, has implications for 'how the community sees itself and the pride it can take in its narrative heritage': '[c]o-production of identity, reflecting the sociological reality that none of us is sole author of ourselves, contributes not only the aesthetic distance that encourages exploration but also the mutual identification of co-producers and audience' (2016, pp. 9-11). The 'built-in distancing' of the reflective, retrospective life story or 'episode' is favoured as it 'does not have to signify the rejection of past selves, nor a sense that one's current identity has sole validity' (Valentine, 2016, p. 9).

2. Content and infrastructure of the collection

OurStory Scotland have captured stories in a variety of different analogue and digital formats:

- **Recorded oral history interviews** (full-length individual life stories; group recordings; short, off-the-cuff interviews, including at public events; public performances of stories): uncompressed .wav sound files with.pdf summaries

compiled by volunteers and associated .jpeg photographs and .tiff scans of images donated by or taken of interviewees.³

- **Handwritten ‘episodes’**: manuscript submissions and transcriptions of stories recorded at public events on paper.
- **Born-digital written personal testimonies and ‘episodes’** (answers to questionnaires, diaries, and observations in response to prompts on specific themes): submissions to Wufoo (SurveyMonkey) online form on OurStory Scotland website.
- **Films of public events**: uncompressed DV files.

The majority of the archival content generated by the OurStory Scotland project is owned and managed by the organisation itself. A small proportion of the collection is held in two separate public collections:

- **Scottish Life Archive, National Museums Scotland**: manuscript ‘episodes’ (x 171), and assorted ephemeral items including posters, postcards, and printed t-shirts from storytelling workshops and public events, c.2005-2006.
- **OurStory Scotland Collection, National Library of Scotland (from 2016)**: oral history interviews, summaries, and associated photographs of interviewees (x 7 as of February 2024), c.2004-2006 (Archives & Manuscript Division); film of Storytelling Ceilidh, Glasgow, 2006 (Moving Image Archive).

It is OurStory Scotland’s intention, as part of the distributed Scotland’s Sounds network through the National Library of Scotland, that where relevant copies of certain oral histories will be deposited both at the National Library and at the appropriate local authority record office (for instance, where a recording was made with a local LGBT+ community group with existing links to their local record office).

The selection process for donations is carried out entirely by OurStory Scotland’s Board and volunteers. Stories are either acquired by specific invitation or gathered at storytelling workshops and other public events, including community arts and Pride festivals; the general process is described in detail in Valentine’s history of the organisation in *History Scotland* (2012b).

Early in the project, Jaime Valentine consulted with Rob Perks, Curator of Oral History and Director of National Life Stories, British Library Sound Archive on oral history recording and archiving techniques (Valentine, 2012a, p. 31). OurStory Scotland closely follow the British Library’s model for producing ‘summaries’ with time stamps, as opposed to full transcripts, for each of their oral histories in order to foreground the importance of listening to the recorded voice. This is a time-consuming process undertaken solely by volunteers, but one which enables the archive’s community to play an important role in preserving, describing, and interpreting the digital content in their own words prior to its transfer to the National Library of Scotland (Valentine, 2020, p. 7).

Storytelling methods were adapted during the Covid-19 pandemic to continue remotely. The recent collection of personal testimonies through an online form was prompted by the first national lockdown and was inspired by the collecting techniques of Mass-Observation

³ In 2004-2005, interviews were recorded on Marantz tape cassettes, which have since been digitised. From 2005 onwards all recordings have been born-digital. In 2020-2021, oral history interviewing was continued during the Covid-19 pandemic remotely using Squadcast.fm (for details see Valentine, 2021).

Communities Online (OurStory Scotland, 2021).⁴ The gathering of retrospective stories in short, off-the-cuff and group interviews and the written personal testimonies OurStory Scotland describe as ‘episodes’ has always been an important part of the project, and is contrasted by Valentine to the soliciting of memory: ‘the idea of personal retention may suggest memory as individual rather than social, with an implication of self-consistency or coherence that is absent from episodes’ (2016, p. 7).

Since 2010, OurStory Scotland have created discrete themed projects to collect and present stories and episodes relating to specific topics of interest or concern for the LGBT+ community in Scotland. Once devised, these themes remain in the repertoire for ongoing storytelling:

- **OurSpace (2008)**: storytelling and exhibition at Kelvingrove Art Gallery and Museum, Glasgow, on the theme of LGBT+ places and spaces; later incorporating Queering the Map.
- **Love Out of Bounds (2010-2012)**: stories of loves untold, ignored, or rejected by people’s family, community, or culture, including people from minority ethnic groups, irrespective of gender and sexuality. In collaboration with the Village Storytelling Centre, Glasgow. Exhibitions at St Mungo Museum of Religious Life and Art, Glasgow, and other libraries and museums in Scotland.
- **Moving Bodies (2014)**: stories concerning body ideals and expectations, sporting bodies, transformative bodies and self-governing bodies. Initially developed for storytelling workshops at Pride House at the 2014 Commonwealth Games.
- **Coming In (2016)**: stories of LGBT+ people coming to Scotland (‘coming out while coming in’) and enhancing its diversity, in response to the xenophobia surrounding the 2016 UK-EU Membership Referendum and its aftermath. In collaboration with LGBT Health & Wellbeing, Connecting Scotland’s Sounds, and National Library of Scotland.
- **Queer Distance (2020)**: online-only storytelling developed in response to the necessity of social distancing during the coronavirus pandemic.
- **Transgressions (2021)**: stories of crossing boundaries of the ‘normal’ or ‘natural’ in relation to gender expectations and ideas of the family and monogamy.

OurStory Scotland organise the digital archive into folders according to nature of recording (i.e. full-length oral histories, group recordings, short interviews, and performance of stories). The full-length oral history interviews have a folder dedicated to each interviewee, except when interviewed as a couple. The other recordings may be subsumed under a particular event (such as The Commonwealth Games) and/or a themed project (such as Love Out of Bounds). Sub-folders of the above include the digital audio files, any digital images of the people/occasion, a scan of the copyright clearance form, and the text summary of the recording.

The data and metadata is kept on hard drives to which OurStory Scotland trustees have access, with regular back-ups and virus scans. The National Library of Scotland have acted as a point of contact to advise on, for instance, the feasibility of archiving different file formats, but do not set parameters as to what can be included in the archive, intervene directly in the management of the digital records or require specific metadata. Copyright clearance forms contain interviewees’ full names and addresses and will be filed separately

⁴ The Mass Observation Project is a national life writing project about everyday life in Britain, and one of the major repositories of longitudinal qualitative social data in the UK. It was an early national collector of personal testimonies relating to LGBT+ lives and experiences in the UK (see Cook, 2017).

to the archive within the Archives & Manuscript Division's internal records upon transfer to the National Library of Scotland.

As part of their remit OurStory Scotland work in partnership with other LGBT+ community organisations to offer training in oral history and archiving methods. This has led to the creation of two separate hybrid archive collections by external organisations, which will be made accessible alongside the OurStory Scotland Collection at the National Library of Scotland in due course:

- **Pink Saltire, '50 Years of Rainbow Activism' (2019-2020)**: oral history project with older LGBT+ activists in Scotland to mark the 50th anniversary of the Stonewall riots, with a podcast and touring exhibition. Funded by The National Lottery Community Fund Scotland.
- **LGBT Youth Scotland, '(Un)seen, (Un)heard' (2023-2025)**: intergenerational oral history and analogue archiving project with LGBT+ young people in Scotland (13-25 years). Funded by The National Lottery Heritage Fund and supported by the National Library of Scotland.

In recent years, perhaps as a result of the extended periods of isolation in which people found themselves during the pandemic, OurStory Scotland have also increasingly acted as a clearing house for LGBT+ individuals and groups seeking advice on preserving analogue archival records. From 2020, this has led to a number of conversations with donors being initiated with Archives & Manuscripts at the National Library of Scotland. The first personal paper archive collection to be transferred is that of Jim Mearns, who recorded a remote OurStory Scotland oral history on his role in the campaign to repeal Clause 2A (Section 28) legislation in Scotland during the 1990s.⁵ There are a myriad of connections – both existing and potential future links to be made – between OurStory Scotland interviewees and existing National Library of Scotland modern archive and manuscript collections, including those of Bob Orr and Sigrid Nielson, co-owners of Lavender Menace, Scotland's first LGBT+ bookshop; Edwin Morgan, poet; and Jo Clifford, playwright. Indeed, OurStory Scotland played an important role in encouraging a more active approach to collecting the records of contemporary LGBT+ Scots at the National Library and initiated the creation of a research guide and directory to LGBT+ archives hosted on the library's main website.⁶

3. Audiences and use of the archive: present and future

OurStory Scotland make interpretation and presentation of the archive through community-led events, exhibitions, and performances fundamental to its creation, as explored in section 1. OurStory Scotland Trustees regularly promote the archive through conferences and other community archive/cultural heritage and LGBT+ networking events. Recent digital engagement activities have included a podcast series comprising extracts from recorded oral history interviews on the theme of 'Childhoods' with introductions from Dom Miller-Graham; the episodes are made available through the usual podcast platforms (Anchor, Spotify, Google Podcasts, Apple Podcasts, etc).

Use of the 7 oral history interviews, summaries, and associated born-digital files at the National Library of Scotland is currently limited to on-site consultation through access copies

⁵ The collection was donated in two separate tranches and also contains material relating to Jim's trade union and Labour Party activism, as well as to his cultural interests (archive references: Acc.14225 and Acc.14357).

⁶ <https://www.nls.uk/collections/topics/lgbt-research-resources/>

on CD-Rs in the reading rooms. To date, access requests and general enquiries about this collection have been received both from academic users (primarily undergraduate and postgraduate students) and other LGBT+ community groups.

The film of the OurStory Scotland Storytelling Ceilidh (2006) is hosted on the National Library of Scotland's Moving Image Archive online catalogue and is available to view in full on-site only.⁷

Workflows and processes for access to born-digital collections within the Archives & Manuscript Division at the National Library of Scotland are still in the process of development. Indeed, metadata and cataloguing practices will to some extent be informed by the needs of the OurStory Scotland Collection. In the future, it is hoped that the user experience will be closer to that of the British Library's sound archive, with searchable metadata (i.e. text copies of the summaries) available to view remotely from the National Library of Scotland's online catalogue and sound files available to be delivered to readers online through a digital asset management system. An ideal scenario could be to have a 'front end' containing a co-curated online exhibition/web resource with short extracts from the oral histories as well as links into the National Library's catalogue, to offer different ways into the archive for everyday users as well as specialist researchers.

The assignation of copyrights within the majority of the oral histories may offer opportunities in terms of remote access, but this remains to be discussed with OurStory Scotland and will be informed by their own approach to audience development and engagement.

4. Challenges

Critiques of the relationship between autonomous queer community archiving work and larger collecting institutions emphasise the precarity of grassroots and post-custodial initiatives within mainstream cultural heritage (e.g. Apple, 2021). In contrast, perhaps, to regional and local LGBT+ community archiving organisations in the UK and continental Europe, OurStory Scotland established arms-length working relationships with national institutions from the outset of the project, thereby ensuring that records were created in line with existing institutional recordkeeping practices and that the archive would always have space within a permanent repository. The Scotland's Sounds network provides an existing model for sustainable, distributed digital archiving of oral histories which complicates the conventional binary between institutional and community-based recordkeeping.⁸

Within the National Library itself, responsibility for the OurStory Scotland Collection sits between two posts in the Archives & Manuscript Division in Edinburgh (Political Collections and Discovery & Access) as well as with the Sound Curator and Moving Image Acquisitions Curator in the Moving Image Archive in Glasgow, offering some level of continuity in the event of staff turnover. The National Library's active cross-departmental LGBT+ Staff Network (established in 2020), through which relationships with LGBT+ community groups are built and maintained beyond the custodial, adds another safety net.

It is notable that this particular project has spanned a period of intense change in the nature of online personal record-keeping and storytelling in the wider culture, with particular implications for LGBT+ testimonies collected before the widespread use of personal networked social media accounts (Chenier, 2015; Cowan and Rault, 2018). Ethics are

⁷ <https://movingimage-onsite.nls.uk/film/9948>

⁸ <https://www.nls.uk/about-us/working-with-others/scotlands-sounds/>

guided from within the community of the archive's participants and donors, rather than being set by external advisors. Valentine notes that the LGBT+ community in Scotland is uniquely positioned to deal with matters such as privacy, given that so many of its members 'have had experience of the benefits and dangers of disclosure' (2016, p 11). Interviewees are explicitly warned to not to 'out' other living individuals at the point of recording their stories, for instance.

While adherence to Data Protection legislation is dealt with according to the Library's normal policies and processes, it is worth noting that considerations of sensitivity and ethics primarily arise from the community and have, in some ways, a greater impact on decision making about redaction and restriction than the legislation. OurStory Scotland carry out their own sensitivity review of each interview and redact sections where deemed necessary to protect living individuals.

Upon transfer to the National Library of Scotland – the point at which the Library became both Data Controller and Processor – the first tranche of 7 interviews (one of which had already been redacted) were also reviewed 'double-blind' by the Political Collections Curator and by a PhD candidate undertaking research towards a Collaborative Doctoral Partnership on the use of automation for sensitivity review in 2019. This drew on the framework used by the Unlocking Our Sound Heritage (UOSH) project at the British Library and assigned each recording a score between 0-5 for various 'sensitivity flags' (e.g. 'Sexuality', 'Medical or health-related information', 'Political opinions').⁹ Scorings were then discussed by both reviewers and the then Digital Archivist (supervisor of the student's CDP project). The National Library of Scotland has since introduced a Sensitivity Appraisal Framework to guide its decision-making in this area.¹⁰ The implementation of the framework in day-to-day processing for modern and contemporary archive collections is also a work in progress; members of the Archives & Manuscripts team meet weekly to discuss matters arising from access and sensitivity review work across the collections, and also feed into a Library-wide steering group on Sensitivity Review.

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⁹ Internal documentation, UOSH Document 6, 'Flag Example Matrix', (c.2019).

¹⁰ <https://www.nls.uk/media/s4afh43u/sensitivity-appraisal-framework.docx>

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